

Exfoliated and Intercalated PMMA/Clay Nanocomposites Synthesized by in situ Polymerization in Supercritical Carbon Dioxide and Ethanol with the Aid of Water

M. D. Hossain, M.T. Islam and K. T. Lim
Pukyong National University
San 100 Yongdang-dong, Nam-Gu, Pusan, 608-739 Korea
ktlim@pknu.ac.kr

SUMMARY

PMMA/montmorillonite clay nanocomposites were synthesized via the free radical polymerization of MMA in the presence of quaternized polysilsesquioxane surfactant-modified clay and AIBN initiator in scCO₂ and ethanol with the aid of water. Initially, clay was cation exchanged with the surfactant to enhance its hydrophobicity and to expand the interlamellar spaces of silicate platelets. Organophilization with 3-D surfactant and a small amount of water reduced the surface energy of the clay dramatically, which promoted miscibility of polymer/clay nanocomposites.

Keywords: poly(methylmethacrylate, montmorillonite clay, nanocomposites, polysilsesquioxan,; intercalation, exfoliation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Polymer-layered silicate nanocomposites have received considerable attention in recent years as an effective method of enhancing thermal stability and improved flame retardant, mechanical, and barrier properties.¹⁻² Montmorillonite, the most preferred and widely used smectic clay is of particular interest because it offers a high aspect ratio (10-1000) and a high surface area. Employing surfactants with simple ion-exchange reactions and subsequent polymerization with a suitable monomer, could achieve different natures of morphologies: intercalated, intercalated and flocculated and exfoliated.³ Exfoliated nanocomposites usually provide the best property enhancement due to the large aspect ratio and surface area of the clay.⁴ There are in reality very few unequivocal examples of the synthesis of exfoliated nanocomposites because the strong electrostatic force between clay layers tends to hold them together and underlie the preferred face-to-face stacking geometry in agglomerated clay tactoids.⁵ On the other hand, partially exfoliated nanocomposites are more readily produced having silicate layers exfoliated into secondary particles which contain several stacked, coplanar layers. Here, we report the synthesis of intercalated and exfoliated PMMA/MMT nanocomposites by in situ polymerization in scCO₂ and ethanol with the aid of water.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Montmorillonite (MMT) was obtained from Gelest, Inc (USA) which has cation exchanged capacity of 92.6 meq/100 g and it was used as received. 3-Chloropropyl trimethoxysilane (97+%) and N,N-dimethyl-n-octylamine were purchased from Aldrich (USA) and were used without additional purification. MMA (Junsei Chem, Japan) was purified by passing the liquids through a neutral alumina column to remove inhibitor and 2, 20-azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) was purified by recrystallization in methanol.

2.2. Synthesis of alkyl ammonium substituted polysilsesquioxane surfactant for MMT modification

Alkyl ammonium substituted polysilsesquioxane surfactant was synthesized by slight modification of the procedure reported elsewhere [6]. Initially, poly-3-chloropropylsilsesquioxane was synthesized by the hydrolytic polycondensation of 3-chloropropyltrimethoxysilane. Then 1.15 g of poly-3-chloropropylsilsesquioxane was mixed with 3.60 g of N,N-dimethyl-n-octylamine, 10 mL of isopropanol and 7.00 g of dimethyl formamide. The mixture was heated at 80 °C for 10 days. Isopropanol and dimethyl formamide were distilled off under vacuum. The oily viscous product was dissolved in a small amount of dichloromethane and precipitated with n-hexane to remove excess amine. After removing amine, a waxy like white product of QPSSQ was collected by drying in vacuum. ¹H NMR analysis showed that 85% of the 3-chloropropyl groups were transformed to quaternized ammonium groups.

2.3. Modification of MMT

Na-MMT (1.0 g) was dispersed in 50 mL of deionized water under vigorous stirring to form a suspension. 0.5 g of QPSSQ surfactant was dissolved in 50 mL deionized water and added to the aqueous suspension. The mixture was stirred for 24 h before it was collected by filtration. The solid precipitate was subsequently washed with water several times until there was no white precipitate observed by adding 0.1 M AgNO₃, indicating an absence of chloride ions. The product was then vacuum-dried at 50 °C for 24 h, ground into powder, and stored in desiccators. The modified clay was denoted as OMMT (organic montmorillonite).

2.4. Preparation of PMMA/MMT nanocomposites

The desired amount of surfactant-modified clay and monomer mixture was first swollen in aqueous ethanol solvent by ultrasonic vibrator for 30 min. The AIBN initiator (1 wt% with respect to monomer) was added to the mixture until completely dissolved. Then, the mixture was placed in a thermo-stated oil bath at 70 °C to carry out polymerization under Argon atmosphere for 12 h. At the end of the polymerization, the mixture was precipitated into methanol, filtered, dried and weighed. For preparing nanocomposites in scCO₂, the desired amount of surfactant-modified clay; monomer and initiator were placed in a stainless steel vessel containing a Teflon-coated magnetic stir bar. Then, 0.034 g of water was added to the reaction vessel. The reactor was pressurized by ISCO syringe pump (Model 260D) containing compressed CO₂ at a pressure of approximately 7 MPa, and then the reaction mixture was heated to 65 °C. As the reaction vessel was heated, the remaining CO₂ was added into the system until the desired pressure of 34.5 MPa was reached. The reactor was sealed and the polymerization was performed for 12 h at 34.5 MPa. After polymerization, the reactor was cooled in ice water, and unreacted

monomer was extracted with liquid CO₂ at a flow rate of 20 mL min⁻¹. The remaining CO₂ was slowly vented at the end of extraction, and the product was collected, dried at room temperature in a vacuum oven overnight and the resultant materials were weight for the determination of monomer conversion.

2.6. Characterization

¹H NMR spectra were recorded using a JNM-ECP 400 (JEOL). The degree of quaternization of the QPSSQ surfactant was determined by ¹H NMR spectra in CDCl₃ solvent. Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) data were collected on a Philips X'pert MPD diffractometer using Cu K α radiation. The XRD patterns were recorded in the range of 1–10° at a scanning rate of 1° min⁻¹. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM; Hitachi S-2400) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM; Hitachi H-7500) were used to observe the morphologies and microstructures of the nanocomposites. The samples were ground and dispersed in ethanol by ultrasonication, and finally it was dropped onto carbon-coated Cu grids for TEM observation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The free radical polymerization of MMA was conducted with 1.0 g of MMA and 0.05 g of OMMT (5% w/w with respect to monomer) in the presence of AIBN initiator at 65 °C in scCO₂ or at 70 °C in ethanol by addition of small amount water. XRD patterns of montmorillonite, OMMT and PMMA/MMT nanocomposites synthesized in different solvent conditions were shown in Fig. 1. By using Bragg equation, the d (001) spacing values of the samples were calculated and used to characterize the layered structure of the polymer/clay nanocomposites. After the cation exchange with QPSSQ, the d-spacing was expanded from 11.8 Å (A) to 16.41 Å (B). As is seen from curves (C) and (D), the d-spacing of PMMA/MMT nanocomposites prepared in ethanol and aqueous ethanol solvent increases to about 20.00 Å. Ethanol is a hydrophilic solvent, this hydrophilicity reduces the surface energy, which results in the dispersion of the clay. Evidently a weak peak is observed in the XRD of the nanocomposites prepared in ethanol. However, the intensity of the peak increased for PMMA/MMT nanocomposites prepared in ethanol/H₂O, indicating they are highly intercalated. This is probably due to the layer by layer assembly of highly dispersed clay platelets or small tactoids onto the surface of PMMA particles. The addition of water in ethanol further reduces the surface energy, which splits larger clay tactoids to small tactoids that give stabilization of composites particles. On the other hand, PMMA/MMT nanocomposites synthesized in scCO₂ show two peaks, where highly intercalated part with larger expanded intergallery spaces dominates. Interestingly, the addition of 1 wt% of water in scCO₂, the clay with larger expanded intergallery space parts disappeared due to the dispersion (more likely exfoliation) of clay inside PMMA matrix, although XRD analysis cannot give any information regarding the exfoliation of the clay. These results support that the addition of a small amount of water in ethanol and scCO₂ leads to the drastic decrease of surface free energy, which facilitates the monomer to enter into intergallery spaces of the clay. The deviation of surface energy of clay was occurred after addition of small amount of water which facilitated the intercalation of monomer.⁶ Incorporation of 3-D structured surfactant into layer silicate has also significant effect on intercalation of monomer. In case of QPSSQ surfactant, alkyl ammonium nitrogen attaches on the clay surface and long octyl chain remains as bending position which triggers some strains inside the clay

galleries. Addition of water molecules decrease electrostatic attraction between clay platelets which facilitates the octyl chain to come in straight alignment position by pushing clay platelets apart and at the same time monomer enters into the intergallery spaces.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of (A) Na-MMT; (B) OMMT; (C) PMMA/MMT nanocomposites prepared in ethanol; (D) aqueous ethanol; (E) scCO₂ and (F) aqueous scCO₂.

Analysis by SEM and TEM (Figure 2) shows that the intercalated nanocomposites were formed when polymerization was conducted in aqueous ethanol solvent, and fully exfoliated clumpy solid products were formed in aqueous scCO₂. The SEM image in Fig. 2 (A) shows that the spherical PMMA/MMT nanocomposites with an average particle diameter of about 20 μm were formed, when polymerization was conducted in aqueous ethanol solvent. These particles show a relatively broad size distribution, presumably due to the ill-defined interaction mechanism between the monomers and insoluble clay platelets as compared to the typical molecular interactions between monomer and soluble surfactants. By TEM observations more supportive information about the microstructures of PMMA/MMT nanocomposites was obtained. In Fig. 2(B), the dark line represents individual silicate layers, whereas the brighter area stands for the PMMA matrix. It can be seen from Fig. 2(B) that the silicate layers of clay platelets have been intercalated into the PMMA matrix, which makes spherical PMMA/MMT nanocomposites beads. For the PMMA/MMT nanocomposites synthesized in aqueous scCO₂ as shown in Fig. 2(C), the silicate layers of clay platelets dispersed by exfoliation throughout the polymer matrix. In Fig. 2(D), TEM results suggest that in aqueous scCO₂ solvent the clay is dispersed more homogeneously in polymer matrix due to high

diffusivity of scCO₂ as well as dispersibility attributed to the lower surface energy of the clay with the addition of 1 wt% of water. Data for PMMA/MMT nanocomposites synthesized in different solvent conditions are given in Table 1.

Fig. 2. SEM images of PMMA/MMT nanocomposites synthesized in (A) aqueous ethanol and in (C) aqueous scCO₂; TEM images of nanocomposites synthesized in (B) aqueous ethanol and in (D) aqueous scCO₂.

Table 1. Data for PMMA/MMT Nanocomposites Synthesized in Different Solvents.

Solvent type	morphology	Structure	d-spacing (Å)
ethanol	clumpy solid	Partially intercalated	19.37
aqueous ethanol	spherical powder	intercalated	19.90, 41.24
scCO ₂	hard clumpy solid	highly intercalated	20.91, 70.04
aqueous scCO ₂	hard clumpy solid	exfoliated	--

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Korea Science and Engineering Foundation (KOSEF) grant funded by the Korea government (MEST) (No. R01-2008-000-21056-0) and the second stage of BK21 Program.

References

- [1] Zeng, Q. H.; Yu, A. B.; Lu, G. Q. ; Paul, D. R. *J. Nanosci. Nanotech.* **2005**, *5*, 10.
- [2] Gilman, J. W.; Jackson, C. L.; Morgan, A. B.; Harris, R. H.; Manias, E.; Giannelis, E. P.; Wuthernow, M.; Hilton, D.; Phillips, S. *Chem. Mater.* **2000**, *12*, 1866.
- [3] Ray, S.S.; Okamoto, K.; Okamoto, M. *Macromolecules* **2003**, *36*, 2355.
- [4] Zeng, C.; Lee, L.J. *Macromolecules* **2001**, *34*, 4098.
- [5] Qian, Z.; Edward, T.S. *Macromolecules* **2005**, *38*, 7967.
- [6] Chojnowski, J.; Fortuniak, W.; Rosciszewski, P.; Werel, W.; Lukasiak, J.; Kamysz, W.; Halasa, R. *J. Inorg. Organomet. Polymer. Mater.* **2006**, *16*, 219.
- [7] Fruzsina, K. ; Laszlo, S. ; Erika, F.; Bela, P. ; *Langmuir* **2006**, *22*, 7848.